

AI's capabilities from the general perspective, and testing boundaries of its application

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Abstract. Recently, the theme of artificial intelligence (AI) received public attention with regard to concerns and fears that AI's capabilities and functionalities can negatively affect and disrupt the present societal and economic fabric of humankind. One of the consequences of high claims about AI is justification in demanding access with little restrictions to private and public resources tech companies need for that. On the other hand, their opponents pinpoint to little evidence but many obstacles making such claims and promises doubtful. In the highly uncertain situations which bear potentially high stakes, like this one, obtaining more definitive and truthful judgment requires exercising analysis based on general proven principles and concepts. Among such approaches are general principles of verification of scientific knowledge, certain philosophical principles and concepts, as well as common sense considerations. Taken together, these tools allow to analyze the subject matter and also setting the stage for such explorations by introducing the necessary restrictions, in order to formulate the problem in definitive and unambiguous terms, understandable by all involved parties. Here, we introduce a framework of such concepts, and also suggest tests, which allow exploring AI capabilities with regard to known claims, potential applications and concerns and fears of critics.

Introduction

Present scientific research overwhelmingly deals with a domain of particular, concrete problems. This is understandable, since much research serves technological and other practical needs. Philosophy of science, the discipline by definition supposed to deal with *general* problems of science, also by and large studies abstract *particulars*, instead of developing a general philosophical scientific framework, as it did in the previous centuries. It is lack of such robust general framework, which presently breeds rather fruitless but long strategic and methodological discussions in some scientific and technological disciplines. At the same time, the best thinkers of the past, including some philosophers, long ago laid foundations, prepared bricks, whole blocks and mortar for creation of such a much needed framework, whose absence becomes more and more evident in the last two decades. Even though it is often felt intuitively by scientists, they rarely have an idea on what basis

such a framework can be created, even less so they think of philosophy as a source capable delivering it. For most of them, philosophy is not even uncharted, but simply unknown and non-existent territory. At the same time, if such a respectable proven framework would exist, many general strategic and methodological problems (often persisting for decades) in different disciplines could be resolved long time ago. Among recent developments, which fall under the same umbrella of general uncertainty and lack of strategic and general guidance, are AI methods, whose image is surrounded by many controversial claims, opinions, concerns and fears. Here, we show how this phenomenon can be analyzed from a philosophical and general consideration perspective.

Applied general notions and concepts

AI methods can generate constructs which, from the perspective of a human mind, have *meaning*. With regard to the subject of this writing, meaning is one of the key notions. So, what is it? A fantastic story can be meaningful, but it is not real in that sense that it does not belong to the realm of objective reality. (One can think of the notion of objective reality as of a world as it is. We have partial knowledge of this world, which is verified and confirmed by our best proven verification methods and experience.) The meaningfulness of such a fantastic story is attributed to the fact that it is based on some aspects, known properties of objective reality, *of different level of generality*. The last emphasis is of importance. A river, a concrete object of reality, can be present in a fantastic story as it is, without generalization, say as river Styx. The notion of societal organization in the assembly of mystical fairy creatures is an abstraction of a higher level, than a river, but this notion is real. And it is this set of abstractions of different levels of generality and of their interrelationships, derived from objective reality, which, once embedded into a fantastic story, makes this story *meaningful* to a human mind. Such fantastic worlds derived from the elements of objective reality (such as concrete objects and generalizations, abstractions of objective reality) have a property of reciprocity, when some inferences obtained in a fantastic world could relate - in some sense - to objective reality. This should not come as a surprise, since derivations done in a fantastic story from a mixture of fantastic inputs and aspects of reality could, indeed, in principle produce a phenomenon with some aspects of reality, which later could be discovered in a real life (for instance, technological advances once envisioned by science fiction writers).

Two other (related to each other) important notions used in this article are *truth* and *practice*, understood in a philosophical sense. Philosophical notions, more often than not, present generalized

and refined common sense. This way we introduced and explained the notion of *meaning* above. So, by and large, we can use the notions of truth and practice in a similar way, as the terms applied in common sense considerations with a self-evident meaning. However, this time we would benefit from a stricter definition of these notions done in philosophy, in particular in philosophy of dialectical materialism. (Introduction to this teaching can be found in [1], while a brief summary of notions, concepts and categories in [2].) Although developed as a philosophical teaching mostly in 19-th and 20-th centuries, its foundations ascend to Ionic philosophers, of which Anaximander was the most prominent one. Even though his original writings did not survive, available references to and quotes from his works, such as the ones presented in [3], indeed relate to foundations of dialectical materialism. The dialectic component of this teaching was later separated - fully or partially, and mostly unknowingly - from the materialistic foundation of this philosophy, and was developed by several prominent philosophers, whose ideas were eventually assembled and further developed into a coherent teaching by Hegel, in his several works. However, instead of materialism it was done on the basis of *objective idealism* (of these works, "Science of Logic" is the most complete and advanced presentation of Hegel's teaching).

There are many philosophical definitions of truth, each accentuating certain aspects of this notion, but none of which could be regarded as a comprehensive one. So, we should rather provide a more elaborate explanation instead of presenting a crispy and laconic quote suitable to be carved in stone. In short - and very schematically - we percept objective reality by our senses and by processing their inputs brain, of which instincts, and mechanisms of their formation, as well as memory, reasoning, are notions widely known to general public. On this basis, our mind synthesizes a view of the outside world, and of ourselves in this world. Our view can be adequate to objective reality to a different degree; from almost totally wrong to a very close one.

But who is the judge of wrongness or validity of a world view of a person, or a group or a society? The answer is given by a category of *practice*. Practice is understood in philosophical sense as interaction of a subjective entity with objective reality, receiving feedback from it, accounting for these inputs, possibly adjusting the view of the entity or a phenomenon the interaction was with, adjusting actions (supposedly making them more efficient) for the next round of interaction, and so on. The following example provides illustration. Suppose one looks in a window and sees a blue sky, green trees and sunshine. And chooses to put light clothes and exits outside. However, in ten seconds the person discovers quite fresh air and realizes that the chosen

clothing is too light for such temperature. So, the person returns home and adds a light jacket. Next exit outside follows, but in two minutes the person turns around the building corner and finds strong chilly wind, which was previously blocked by the building. So, the next return to home follows, the light jacket is replaced with a warmer one, and a hat is added too. Now, the person is more or less *adequately* equipped for the weather, achieving this *iteratively* and *incrementally* in successive steps through interaction with the surrounding environment. Or, in philosophical terms, through *practice*. This term includes all the described actions. (Note that the concept of practice includes many more considerations.)

The emphasized words "*iteratively*" and "*incrementally*" are of importance, because they reflect on fundamental properties of knowledge acquisition in general. This is how we cognise the world, the objective reality - bit by bit, in successive steps, acting in each next step based on results of previous steps, on previous knowledge. (Of course, the actual process is more complicated, with many inner inserts of iterations and increments into each larger iteration, which in turn can overlap. Besides, the steps in rare instances become so large and so far reaching that they create *qualitatively* new knowledge; in such cases we speak of *heuristic* discoveries.) Even if one makes mental deduction, in order for it to be adequate to objective reality, such deduction must be based on previous knowledge obtained and verified *by practice*. Without verification by practice, series of such mental deductions will produce results diverted from objective reality. To which extent, depends on the subject, but the important thing is that such diversion is inevitable in principle. (We will soon explain why this is so.) If interaction with objective reality at some iteration produces results within an accepted margin of error, one can say that the knowledge used for actions in this iteration was *adequate*, i. e. corresponded to objective reality with certain accuracy. Or, in philosophical terms, it was *truthful*. This fundamental principle of knowledge acquisition and verification (including of course verification of validity of our actions), is formulated in dialectical materialism as "*Practice is a criterion of truth*".

Practice is a criterion of truth, but AI in its present form assumes a limited feedback, nor a fully iterative and incremental approach in the described form, which is the foundation of *any* practical activity aimed to optimal real results. Iterations and increments relate to a particular task, and the more they are specific for the task, the more meaningful and effective they are, while AI methods are based upon the opposite approach - extractions from voluminous data, and the more voluminous data are, the better results it is supposed to produce.

What happens when one detaches knowledge acquisition from practice, say using purely theoretical deductions? Suppose we make the first iteration on the basis of verified knowledge; in other words, on the basis of objective reality. The result is new knowledge, but this time it is unverified by practice, so that part of it may be untrue. This knowledge was obtained from a spectrum of all possible outcomes, which differ from one another, and so the obtained (or chosen) outcome has a probability p_1 to be true, which is less than one (since we have other possible different outcomes). For the second deduction step, we have a similar probability p_2 choosing the right outcome that the obtained knowledge is true. However, the total probability that the knowledge obtained after the second step is true is now $P_2 = p_1 \times p_2$. Applying similar considerations to next steps, and using method of mathematical induction, we will eventually obtain for the total probability P_n that the obtained knowledge at step n is true $P_n = p_1 \times p_2 \dots p_n$. Since each $p_i < 1$ ($i=1,2,\dots,n$), $P_n \rightarrow 0$ when $n \rightarrow \infty$, that is the probability to have a truthful deduction without verification at each successive step tends to *zero*. So, unverified theoretical deductions divert from the truth, and the more such steps are, and the less probability that the obtained results at each step are true, the sooner the results of deductions divert from the truth. This is one of the reasons of crisis in modern physics, when theoretical deductions are not verified by experiments, or, in a more general sense, by practice, which besides experiments may include other means of verification, such as general criteria of verification of scientific truths and results of other related scientific disciplines.

The presented notions and categories by no means exhaust the philosophical apparatus, which is relevant to the discussed problems of AI, neither the presentation of introduced notions is comprehensive. However, for the purposes of basic analysis of AI capabilities and limitations we will restrict ourselves by this introduction.

AI in a nutshell

"Artificial intelligence" term is rather a hype word intended for the promotion of technology to gain certain benefits, and for attracting interest of general public, stirring some emotional response, amazement. Specialists have a more realistic view of this technology and use a more appropriate and accurate (in their view) term "machine learning" (ML). Real intelligence assumes some core *essence* (this is also a philosophical term, but we won't elaborate on that), which then can be presented in different ways - lexically, through images, graphs, orally, in writing, by movements

(recall choreography), music, and so on, and by different combinations of thereof. ML methods by and large produce their results the other way around; from large amount of *data* (which by and large are *results*, but not the essence) they extract *patterns* and then, mimicking these patterns, produce results. Due to the semblance of the *form* of thus obtained results to constructs obtained by traditional way from objective reality, the results *may* acquire *meaning*. The chances of obtaining meaning increase with introduction of more sophisticated analysis of structure and content of training datasets, such as multilayered analytics, certain data filtration and data enhancements, and many more possible improvements contributing to the purpose, so that some output products indeed may amuse at a first glance.

So, ML works by *analogy*, *by mimicking*. By and large, the capability of ML is how far some analogy of input data can be extended, how far it can go from original creations, which generally could be an object, a pattern, a structure, a framework, a system, a concept, a theory, a world view, a system of concepts and structures, and so on. At the core of its functioning, ML can produce meaning *only* by analogy, by pattern, by template. It approaches the *content*, the *essence* from the *outside*, not from *inside*; through a *form*, but not through the core, fundamental ideas. Its results originate not from within the most inner core of the subject or phenomenon in question, not from the *essence*, which then could pass successively through the layers surrounding the core of the *content*, adding more elements for consistency, description of relationships of inner parts, for presentation, etc. The traditional intellectual activity is an iterative and incremental process in many dimensions; this also includes continuously going back and forth from particular details (data) to generalizations, which effectively results in continuous reformulation of the problem and its wrapping, restructuring into a more definitive and concise form (essence). (This is one of the reasons why the actual intellectual process is so efficient compared to ML, even if we disregard incomparable energy expenditures of both processes.) In intellectual process particular details (data) and their generalizations, conceptualization are two inseparable aspects of knowledge acquisition, and so both always coexist in *unity*. In the traditional intellectual development, once first generalizations are made, there is a flow of conclusions and deductions from the most *inner* layers - generalizations and core ideas - to the outside layers of lesser generalized knowledge and details surrounding the core content. In this regard, as it was said already, ML starts from the most *outer* layers, from details and less generalized knowledge, thus catching the most visible features of the *form*, and thus creating, framing an *appearance*, composed of main outer features, so to say, and

then adds finer structure and details to this outer appearance (provided algorithms are able to penetrate to deeper layers of structure, form and content). However, thus created structural appearance is not the frame of the core or of the entire structure, of key, fundamental ideas - they are hidden from ML, inaccessible to it, because ML, even if it accidentally touches them, is unable to make a sound and definitive judgment that this is indeed a set of *core* ideas. This is because ML creates *analogy* for the *whole* how it is presented through the data - for all layers at once, or from *outside* layer to the adjacent *inner* layer, and so on, while the layers are defined rather arbitrary with regard to the *actual* structure of the object or phenomenon in question.

For instance, in case of linguistic constructs ML is trained on descriptive elements assembled in different meaningful combinations - many combinations. Such, words considered separately compose a dictionary, but bound together in sentences and other linguistic constructions by ML algorithms, they could create new meanings, *similarly, analogously* to the texts algorithms were trained on. And this is rather all that ML does. It cannot make *judgment* about the content of constructed texts. For instance, ML can construct texts against ML. In this regard, this tool is as intelligent as pliers.

Presently, ML is developed as an evermore sophisticated *tool*, without giving due thought how this tool works in innermost meaning, and what capabilities are defined by these innermost meanings. ML today is somewhat analogous to a Babylonian way of thinking, while real efficiency and most valuable results come from the Greek (synthetic) way of thinking, which is based on generalizations. Let us illustrate this statement by an example. Babylonians knew about Pythagorean triples, and indeed collected many of them. However, they did not know about the general solution of the equation $a^2 + b^2 = c^2$, which produces these triples [4], or Pythagorean Theorem. How much information has to be added, of what kind and how far from the subject matter (up to almost irrelevant to the subject), in order for ML to make such generalizations? And then one should compare the solution process of the same problem by a human mind.

To explore ML with regard to human brain, we need either to know how the brain functions, and / or we can do comparison based on the products of ML and of the mind. Although much is known about the brain neurophysiology, it is probably still fragmented knowledge for such a precise analysis, and for the purpose of this general study we would rather obtain more reliable results using knowledge of products of these entities (of course, in certain aspects neurophysiology could provide useful insights, which should not be ignored).

ML and human brain

The products of brain are substantially diverse in nature, meaning that the brain produces *qualitatively* different products, from simple registration of observations to heuristic scientific discoveries. Brain has instincts embedded into a reptilian brain and a lower mammalian brain (which are parts of a human brain), as well as acquires instincts by training. The brain is composed of different specialized regions working on different tasks, but it also can mobilize resources of different regions to work on the same problem. So, in a brain, different regions and different mechanisms work together, influencing each other in a cooperative or disturbing way, and thus serving diverse needs of an entire organism.

One of the most distinctive evolutionary features of human brain is that it was forming in the environment with scarce information, and so it was trained to make deductions, inferences, associations on the basis of *particular, concrete* and *few* inputs, as well as to be highly *selective* in searches of new information (since search requires resources, which were scarce). ML is of the opposite paradigm - its methods are thirsty for data, and it is their inherent essence that they need lots of and lots of data. This fundamental difference in ML approaches and workings of human brain requires a thorough and comprehensive study, while presently this difference is masked. Even more so - there are unfounded assertions that ML and human brain work on the same fundamental principles. However, the aforementioned facts of human brain evolution, and just of its mere functioning, show that the human mind works differently than ML methods. Saying the opposite would mean cutting off other alternative approaches to emulate artificial intelligence. And there are many of them, given the diversity of intelligence mechanisms and of their combinations human mind possesses and exercises in very different situations. It makes direct sense to study such alternative ways, especially the ones which closer emulate human brain workings (since despite all drawbacks this is a proven achievement).

For ML development, such considerations could be important too. How much info? There should be an optimum amount of information even for gluttony ML algorithms. In additions, maybe ML approaches should include selective searches of information, as humans do.

We already mentioned that ML methods work by *analogy*, by *mimicking*. So, it would be logical to expect that the less analogous the subject is, the less suitable or optimal is ML for the purpose. Such is precise creative engineering, problems of natural sciences, like physics, mathematics - in

other words in the subjects exercising well defined logic, such as the logic of physical laws, or logic of mathematical abstractions. And indeed, with regard to differences between the human brain thinking and the ML methods workings, ML methods demonstrate poor performance when it comes to handle logical constructions, like in mathematical logic. Human mind, on the other hand, invented the formal apparatus, and most people have no problem with day-to-day logical constructions. This fact should be paid close attention to, because formalized apparatus of logic is simple and logical operations are well defined. Could this be a one more indication that a human brain and ML methods work indeed differently?

Although we were mentioning mostly the human brain, for better understanding, we should rather talk about an entire self-sufficient organism, of which brain is an important part. This self-sufficiency of existence in the surrounding environment assumes that at any given moment the organism's behaviour is adequate enough to survive, and that the organism is taking into account (consciously and subconsciously) numerous checks and balances, restrictions and permissions of all kinds imposed by the outer environment and organismal demands and physical and mental limitations. For that, the organism's physiological and intellectual activity has to be organized in a certain way, which necessarily includes, at a minimum, executive, monitoring and controlling functions (and the appropriate systems), which continuously interact with each other. Can ML provide such systems and their joint functioning? Assuming that ML is supplied by inputs from sensors and other sources of information, it can provide some summary of the situation and typical inferences, if it was trained on a sufficient amount of data. So, in this sense, in principle, monitoring is possible by ML methods. However, such summaries will be based on *past* information, while the environment and the object itself change all the time. (The famous phrase by Heraclitus "No one can enter the same river twice", which reflects on the fundamental property of matter that it is *always* in motion. And this motion can be *evolutionary*, with slow changes, which ML methods in some instances can adopt, but also matter changes *revolutionary*, and in this case the present ML approaches give rather very little.) In monitoring, usually single non-ordinary events are of importance, while training algorithms for non-ordinary events is difficult, for several reasons.

These obstacles also present, and more new arise when we consider controlling and executive functions, for which *specificity* of inputs is even more important in order to make an optimal decision. Making optimal decisions, in turn, requires accounting for specificity of a particular situation, of hierarchy of influencing factors and their interaction, and specificity of methods used

for finding solution and its implementation. Such *specificity*, in fact, is in conflict with *generality* of big training datasets, required for application of ML methods, and accordingly with the generality embedded into constructs created by these methods.

So, it would be logical to assume that ML methods should be subjected to tests showing their capability with regard to monitoring, controlling and executing, as well as other numerous functions human brain can perform. The contra-argument (though a very radical one) could be that ML is an entirely new class of intelligence, and so it should be exempted from such tests and comparisons with what human brain does. Despite the obvious ridiculousness of this argument, let us pinpoint that human intelligence is the only one we have more or less comprehensive knowledge about. Given the well established fact that intelligence can do a great good, as well as a great harm, its development should be framed in the terms society understands, and within the boundaries the society can monitor and control. Furthermore, who has ever established that the human intelligence and its properties are only human brain specific? On the contrary, even monitoring, controlling and executive functions we mentioned look rather like the features *any* type of intelligence should be able to perform.

Heuristic discoveries

Probably the pinnacle of any intelligence is ability to do heuristic discoveries. Can ML do heuristic discoveries? At a first glance, there is nothing in its methods which would allow assuming this, but who knows. Let us take for clarity examples of heuristic scientific discoveries, such as Archimedes law (that weight of water pushed out by floating body is equal to weight of this body), Second Newton's law of mechanics (that acceleration is directly proportional to applied force and inversely proportional to body's mass). Could ML algorithms, even in principle, deduce these heuristically discovered physical laws given the knowledge preceded to the discoveries? In our view, the answer is no, but these are technically feasible tests. It also possible to emulate similar scenarios with other important discoveries, such as recognition of possibility of erroneous folding of proteins, which took for the scientist about two decades to be acknowledged. General growth mechanisms [5,6] is another candidate for such a test. Metabolic allometric scaling mechanisms in [7,8] also present an opportunity for.

The specific of heuristic discoveries (and this is why they are called heuristic) is that they originate seemingly on a very thin basis, almost from nowhere, in a one big leap, which lands the

subject matter into a *qualitatively* different, unexplored territory. In this regard, we see a conflict between the foundation of ML methods as trained on big datasets, and very small, restricted and loosely related, and in fact often conflicting inputs from the previous mainstream studies. In this regard, the situation with general growth mechanisms presented in [5,6] is illustrative, since these results are indeed in conflict with overwhelming biochemical approaches to the study of biological phenomena.

In line with the said above the following question comes to mind: Can ML, in principle, be used for solving crisis in modern physics? This could be interesting development because of the tight knot of problems of different nature, which exacerbated this crisis. Here we can find problems of scientific methodology, general philosophical problems of epistemology (gnosiology), including role of practice, as well as the need to work with philosophical categories of form, content, measure, which are very much applicable to the present situation in physics. (They are also applicable to functioning of organizational structure in research establishments, which is apparently too part of the crisis).

Thus, heuristic discoveries, in the described context, present excellent testing, exploration, and likely limiting grounds for ML methods.

True and false, or neither one

One of the often mentioned dangers of ML is their ability to stealthily construct untrue information intermixed with true facts and conclusions, so that the recipient of such spoiled information takes it as a wholly true one. It's a great tool for unscrupulous politicians and businesses to control the population and state resources, including other states. This is another lucrative ground for ML methods testing - could they discover false information in general, and false information constructed by ML methods in particular? How can humans counteract such (literally) propaganda machines?

Ability (or presently most likely inability) of ML methods to discover untrue content is a revealing testing benchmark. On one hand, it could clarify and address the public concerns and fears. On the other hand, it will clearly show where the capabilities of ML really stand. (The third consequence, which also can be deduced in other proposed tests, could be showing ways of further development of ML methods and of their improvement.)

ML generated texts and responsibility for them

This is rather common sense that only *responsible* statements aiming at truth contribute to adequate perception of the world and its progress. However, this is not the case with media outlets these days, not to say about many private statements in the social media. But the same situation was in the past as well, when truth was constantly bent in favour of narrow private or group interests. So, before applying the notion of responsibility to ML generated texts, people should make an order with their own statements, more or less clearly defining what kind of responsibility incur false statements, both intentional and unintentional. Of course, much is done already in legal practice, and some practices are even fixed in laws. However, given the present situation with ML, the scope of such practices certainly requires extensions and maybe even new chapters, as well as education of the general public. In a nutshell, *responsible* statement should mean that the issuer takes some kind of *responsibility* (ethical, legal, moral, social, etc) for the statement. If this is a lie, certain procedures, even legal ones, can be applied.

In case of a ML generated false statement, the computer of course cannot be responsible. However, the responsibility then lies with human(s) which initiated such generation. Same as with humans, the generated lie can be intentional or unintentional, and can be a result of successive actions of different people. In this regards, the application of responsibility through available instruments is very similar as if this was a human generated false statement.

Of course, there are many possible scenarios, but even from the said above it is clear that (a) either these are human or ML generated false statements, the notion of responsibility can and has to be applied; (b) there are already mechanisms in place which (maybe with some changes and adjustments) can be used to exercise responsibility for the false and misleading information in case of ML generated texts.

Conclusion

Presently the results of ML sometimes can amaze indeed, at least some people - to the extent of mystery, how this could be? However, the same amazement often comes from natural phenomena (for instance, regular patterns on animal skins), which while their reason is unknown also could give rise to the same mystical feelings, but when explained (say, by bifurcation equations) lose this mystical veil. It is deeper understanding of ML workings and its limitations, which will give knowledge of ML's boundaries and capabilities, and will explain and remove many presently

confusing (and not rarely intentionally supported) things about ML capabilities. However, until this is done, ML products should be clearly separated, maybe even branded accordingly, from the similar products of human intelligence; not only for the humankind, but also for the ML methods good.

We presented considerations, which form the philosophical basis for an objective, unbiased study of ML technology with regard to its capabilities and possible effects on society. Using this basis, we proposed areas of testing real capabilities of ML methods. Given the obtained inferences, we conclude that ML capabilities at present are exaggerated, mostly for commercial and promotional reasons, and the known high claims have not much ground to be taken as true even as a potential development. This brings a need for a wide and unbiased discussion of the subject by all concerned parties.

With regard to an idea that ML methods represent a true mechanism human intelligence is created by, we found that ML rather mimics the *form* of human thoughts, but cannot recreate an entire structure of a thought in all its dimensions. Some people indeed produce texts in the same manner as ML does - by analogy. However, normally the human thought process is a way more deeper and includes many more dimensions, which ML methods cannot explore *in principle* (as it is almost surely the case with heuristic thinking).

And finally, this paper could also serve as a valuable example of how to approach general problems using robust, proven philosophical teachings, and in particular philosophy of dialectical materialism. This philosophy, which unites in itself the most adequate to objective reality philosophical teachings materialism and dialectics, is a very adequate and tested foundation for creation of philosophical scientific framework. The modern science is rather submerged to practical and concrete problems (and this trend remains even when scientific studies deal with abstract notions). A need in such a framework is definitely present, and it is an acute one. However, the overwhelming majority of scientists even do not consider philosophy as a possible toolset for creation of such a framework, while in many instances having no alternatives but very doubtful, introduced from scratch considerations of self-proclaimed gurus. Unfortunately, modern Western philosophers themselves much contributed to this situation, besides other “sins” also allowing to reject great philosophical teachings of the past, like Hegel’s philosophy, dialectical materialism, by real adventurers seeking nothing but fame and profit for themselves in the heat of the moment. (For

instance, some of them use the only argument that Hegel's teaching should be rejected because they do not understand it [9]!). However, the heritage of the philosophical past is not dead, and it still can be used to a great benefit of humankind, not to a lesser extent as once philosophy did for the development of science and human reasoning. With population growth, and especially because of the greater resources available and accordingly increasing complexity of life, progressively more and more general problems will appear, and the use of proven philosophical doctrines for understanding the situation and finding solutions will be the most optimal approach, far superior to any other alternative. But for that, the science of philosophy has to be revived first of all.

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Competing interests

There is no conflict of interest.

Data availability

No data were generated or analysed.

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Ethical approval

This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed by any of the authors.

Informed consent

This article does not contain any studies with human participants performed by any of the authors.